

“MedWays Cilento” project: a culture-led regeneration strategy for human and sustainable development

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Abstract

Following the pandemic caused by COVID-19, the crisis has mainly affected the most vulnerable communities. It is therefore necessary to understand what the most urgent actions are to be taken at local level to respond adequately to this phenomenon. In this context, has become clear the fragility of large urban centers compared to the greater resilience of small communities in smaller centers. In particular, this virus has highlighted that the resilience of these territories is not only linked to the health conditions of the people (who in normal conditions are statistically better than the inhabitants of the metropolis), but it is also the result of interconnected factors concerning economic, environmental, social and cultural aspects.

On the basis of these considerations, the project MedWays Cilento was born with the aim of giving an interdisciplinary and concrete answer to these great questions, taking as a model one of the territories that has assumed the values of integrity and authenticity as foundation of its lifestyle. This is an experimental project based on culture as a fundamental element on which to invest in order to develop a sustainable human development strategy for the preservation and the regeneration of Cilento’s cultural, environmental and social capital, also activating processes of economic growth.

Keywords: cultural heritage, human and sustainable development, “slow” approach.

Introduction

«*Culture is a transformative force for community regeneration*»: this is what the European Commission stated in its document “A new European agenda for culture” (European Commission, 2018). The Pandemia has highlighted the lack of resilience that characterizes our overall organizational structure and perhaps precisely that of the economically wealthier areas. The economic model of the latter is based on the relocation of activities and has proven to be very weak compared to sudden events such as lockdown. On the contrary, small urban centers have shown that their economic model, more territorialized in geographical space, is more resilient to crises and manages to ensure the survival of small communities for longer periods. In addition to the differences between the two economic models, there are other elements that represent resilience factors: they concern all the “connections” that the communities have established with the place where they live, recognizing the cultural, social, environmental, economic value of their own heritage. This recognition of heritage as a “resource” by communities is a decisive step to strengthen social cohesion, improving the quality of life of the population and triggering economic development processes (Onesti, 2015; Pinto et al., 2019). The more a landscape is dense with relations and

exchanges, the more the landscape/cultural heritage considered as a “common good” encourages the creation of a “community of relations”, which is an important element in determining the quality of life, but also in generating new economic value chains. *«What constitutively connects community and territory is the nature of the common good that they embody: the relational, holistic nature of being in common that is expressed both in the landscape and in the community that is responsible for it and interprets it and finds itself formed»* (Bonesio, 2009). The relationship that really ties a community to a place goes beyond the physical belonging to a ‘given’ place but includes an active dimension in building a sense of belonging through a conscious choice that recognizes in a given landscape the visible expression of collective identity values. The *«‘belonging’ we are talking about implies [...] mutual interaction and not a power relationship of one party (man) over another (the environment)»* (Maddalena, 2014).

«The concept of heritage community is considered as self-defined: by evaluating and wishing to transmit certain aspects of cultural heritage, in interaction with others, an individual becomes part of a community» (Council of Europe 2005, art.2).

Knowledge and use of heritage are part of citizens’ right to participate in cultural life (United Nations, 1948) and contributes to an identity process, which is fundamental for human development and a resource for achieving cultural diversity and promoting intercultural dialogue. This process of identification between community and place where it lives contributes to the creation of the so-called “heritage community”, which is identified by the Convention as *«the set of people who attribute values and specific aspects to cultural heritage, and who wish, in the framework of public action, to support them and pass them on to future generations»* (Council of Europe 2005, art. 2b). This highlights the social value of cultural heritage, which becomes the element that characterizes and holds a community together.

The Convention stresses the importance of considering cultural heritage as an individual and collective responsibility, shared by public authorities at all levels, but also by businesses, civil society and citizens. In other words, the community itself can define and qualify what heritage is and organize its management as a common resource. In this sense, the Council of Europe through the Faro Convention marks a turning point in the management of the immense cultural heritage that we have at our disposal: it ratifies the willingness of States to support and promote integrated governance policies for the administration and conservation of cultural heritage.

The conservation of this heritage is not an end in itself but aims to promote the well-being of individuals and society as a whole by continuing to explore all dimensions of our living: time, space as well as the active role and significance of our surroundings (Council of Europe, 2014b).

The stronger the link between community and context, the more they will be able to react to catastrophic events and that determine significant differences in the reaction ability of communities, readapting their organization, incorporating change and transforming it into an opportunity for rebirth and renewal.

Starting from this premise, the project Medways Cilento aims to highlight the role of value of cultural heritage for sustainable and resilient human settlements, as recognized also in international documents and agendas (UNESCO, 2011, 2013; UNISDR, 2015; United Nations, 2015).

The main objective of the project is to enhance the value of the territory of Cilento by launching actions capable of enhancing its cultural heritage/cultural landscape with a view to human sustainable development and respectful of the intrinsic value of these places.

In this perspective, the project aims to promote a development model based on the needs expressed by communities and other local stakeholders (institutions, local authorities, training bodies, associations, volunteering, etc.) to start a process of individuals and communities growth and awareness, to full realize the local human capital with whole positive effects at cultural, social economic and environmental level.

The MedWays Cilento project aims to give an interdisciplinary and concrete answer to these great questions posed by contemporary challenges starting from Cilento, an area in the province of Salerno, located in the southern part of the Campania region (Italy), and declared World Heritage Site by UNESCO. It represents one of the territories that has made the values of integrity and authenticity as foundation of its way of life, demonstrating how this model has proved to be a winner in history and how it is an essential resilience factor in formulating long-term development strategies.

The research group proposes an experimental project for the elaboration of a sustainable and human-centred development strategy for the protection, regeneration and valorisation of the cultural and natural capital of Cilento, through specific actions carried out by the local communities. Through the implementation of these actions the project aims to activate a whole regeneration process to make the territories more *«inclusive, safe, resilient and sustainable»* (United Nations, 2015, Goal 11).

The project has been elaborated and written by the undersigned together with Luigi Fusco Girard (Emeritus Professor at the University of Naples "Federico II"), Olimpia Niglio (Professor at Hokkaido University), Anny Errico-del Mercato (president of the ARF ART association) and Antonia Gravagnuolo (Researcher at National Research Council - Institute for Research on Innovation and Services for Development and Manager of Research Laboratory on "Human-centred, Creative and Circular City").

The research group is composed of the following partners:

- Laboratory of Research on Creative and Sustainable City (Department of Architecture, University of Naples "Federico II"), Superintendence of Archaeology, Fine Arts and Landscape of the Provinces of Salerno and Avellino,
- Central Institute for Intangible Heritage (Ministry of Cultural Heritage and Activities and Tourism, Rome),
- ARF ART- Association for Research and Training on the Restoration of Historical and Artistic Heritage of the Territory,
- Research Laboratory on "Human-centred, Creative and Circular City" (National Research Council - Institute for Research on Innovation and Services for Development),
- Municipality of San Mauro Cilento.

Moreover, the project is receiving letters of support from the municipalities belonging to the Alento-Monte Stella area, corresponding to the so-called "Ancient Cilento".

The creation of a partnership, supported both institutionally and locally, is the first step to develop a shared development strategy supported by the responsibility and commitment that each partner will assume in the project.

This is where the theme "MedWays" comes from: a "road of the Mediterranean", an axis that aims to connect the Cilento municipalities through a culture-based strategy conducted in synergy between expert knowledge and local stakeholders, to discover, preserve and enhance the cultural heritage of Cilento from which to start a process of growth, including also the economic one.

GEOGRAPHICAL CONTEXT

Until the creation of the “National Park of Cilento, Vallo di Diano and Alburni” the territory of Cilento was identified among the villages at the foot of Monte Stella, that is part of the Baronìa del Cilento of the main branch of the Sanseverino, then Princes of Salerno. In fact, the name came from its position seen from Naples: “cis - Alentum”, on this side of the river Alento. Then, at the end of the 19th century, the toponym attracted the area of the former barony of Novi (the Lucania valley and its neighbours) to the east of the river, so that area is distinguished from the entire national park and takes the name of “Ancient Cilento”¹. It includes eighteen municipalities that are located around the Monte Stella (San Mauro Cilento, Laureana, Stella, Torchiara, Pollica, Serramezzana, Omignano, Sessa Cilento, Montecorice, Stella, Mercato Cilento, Perdifumo, Casal Velino, Rutino, Lustra, Prignano Cilento, Ogliastro Cilento, S.Maria di Castellabate) and five adjacent municipalities (Perito, Orria, Cicerale, Salento, Castelnuovo Cilento, Ascea). Currently for objective reasons it has been decided to extend Cilento to a large part of the southern coastal and inland province of Salerno.

Cilento is in the southern part of the Campania region (Italy) and is part of Salerno province. Since 1991, following the establishment of the “National Park of Cilento and Vallo di Diano”, a large part of the territory of Cilento is under protection. The protected area includes about 181.000 hectares of land, 8 mountain communities and 80 municipalities and is classified as the second largest National Parks in Italy. In the National Park of Cilento and Vallo di Diano 118.316 hectares are classified in the “Rete Natura 2000”, an EU-wide ecological network established under the Habitat Directive 92/43/EEC to ensure the long-term maintenance of threatened or rare natural habitats and species of flora and fauna at EU level. In the Park there are 28 Sites of Community Interest (SIC), established under Habitat Directive and 8 Special Protection Areas (ZPS), established under Directive 79/409/EEC (Birds Directive), all included in the Mediterranean Biogeographical Region.

Fig.1. and Fig.2.: (on the left) Cilento territory and (on the right) Overlapping of the geographical extension of the Ancient Cilento [Re-elaboration of the author from Google Maps].

¹ <https://it.wikipedia.org/wiki/Cilento>

In 1997 the Park was included in the prestigious network of Biosphere Reserves of the UNESCO program “MaB” (Man and Biosphere). In 1998 it was inscribed on the UNESCO World Heritage List and elevated to a Reserve of It is considered a “sanctuary of nature” and “living landscape” as a rare crossroads of civilizations, natural species, and peoples. Magnificent result of the combined work of nature and man, the Park is characterized by the presence of coastal, mountain and valley environments, for the extraordinary richness of vegetation, for a high degree of biological diversity of the species and for the exceptional traces of history from the Palaeolithic to the present day. Unspoilt coastlines, rocky cliffs, ruggedly beautiful hills, paths, waterways, mysterious caves, increase the appeal of these territories, the ideal place for a regenerated journey in nature to (re)discover a priceless heritage.

RECOVERY AND ENHANCEMENT OF THE CULTURAL HERITAGE/CULTURAL LANDSCAPE OF CILENTO

The diversity of the territorial context has therefore had a strong impact on how local communities adapt to the environment and how they exploit resources. For this reason, the project aims to cross the territory of Cilento taking more directions and interpreting the different municipal realities as “nodes” of a relational network in which the connections are still latent or sometimes even non-existent. Currently the coastal strip and the hinterland live as two parallel realities, totally disconnected from each other, between which it is necessary to rebuild the links. To do this, it is necessary to develop a strategy that is capable of reconnecting in a unified vision the cultural identity that binds the different realities of Cilento but, at the same time, is able to adapt to each of them, tracing the synergies, unexpressed and potential, that could be established between them. In this way, the logic of the network would favor the creation of connections and synergies also between realities that, although belonging to the same territorial context, are very different from each other because they have declined the same cultural identity with different outcomes strongly linked to the territorial context that influenced them. This, rather than representing a push for homologation, is instead an aspiration to interpret cultural diversity as a wealth to be valued, which finds its reason for being precisely in the interaction with the other components of the same system.

In this perspective, the role of MedWays Cilento is to frame the municipalities of Cilento in a unified strategic vision capable of enhancing the individual specificities basing on the synergies activated thanks to the network with other realities.

The theme of “Medways” wants to start a training process on the cultural memory of ancient Cilento as a foundation for the elaboration of future scenarios. These places have always been characterized by a particular connection between natural and cultural capital, which can still be read in some fragments of these “ancient” landscapes that still preserve a specific cultural and naturalistic identity. It is therefore necessary to read these connections by taking the approach of the “*Historic Urban Landscape*” defined in the 2011 “UNESCO Recommendations” *«as the result of a historic layering of cultural and natural values and attributes, extending beyond the notion of “historic centre” or “ensemble” to include the broader urban context and its geographical setting. This wider context includes notably the site’s topography, geomorphology, hydrology and natural features, its built environment, both historic and contemporary, its infrastructures above and below ground, its open spaces and gardens, its land use patterns and spatial organization, perceptions and visual relationships, as well as*

all other elements of the urban structure. It also includes social and cultural practices and values, economic processes and the intangible dimensions of heritage as related to diversity and identity» (UNESCO, 2011).

This definition is the starting point for developing a sustainable development strategy that integrates the objectives of heritage and landscape conservation and those of social and economic development. The key principle of “sustainable development” is to preserve and regenerate ecological-environmental, economic-financial and social capital, following a holistic-systemic and multidimensional approach that integrates economy, ecology, society, territory, technology, institutions.

The project Medways Cilento takes the unifying approach of the Historic Urban Landscape as a prism or lens to elaborate a systemic vision of reality and its transformation, including all the complex interdependencies between the different perspectives, respect to which it is possible to interpret the “Cilento system”.

Fig.3. and Fig.4.: two beautiful views of Cilento’s landscape. The hills of Cilento are covered by extensive olive groves (on the left), while the coastal strip is characterized by a wild look and crystal-clear waters (on the right) (Photos by Olimpia Niglio).

The Historical Urban Landscape approach considers cultural diversity and creativity as key resources for human, social and economic development and provides the tools to manage physical and social transformations and ensure that contemporary interventions are harmoniously integrated with heritage and landscape in a historical environment and take into account regional contexts. It draws lessons from the traditions and perceptions of local communities while respecting the values of national and international communities. The systemic nature of the Urban Historical Landscape approach makes the “integrated conservation” of heritage/cultural landscape a “productive activity”, able to increase values in multiple dimensions while respecting their integrity and avoiding their alteration. This perspective is placed in the respect of the Italian civil legal tradition, whose peculiarity is in having recognized the union between landscape and cultural heritage. The recognition of this “endiadi” (the fusion of two elements to express one

concept) is fulfilled in Article 9 of the Italian Constitution: «*The Republic promotes the development of culture and scientific and technical research. It protects the landscape and the historical and artistic heritage of the Nation*».

The elements that substantiate the diversity of the Cilento system, and that represent its richness, constitute as many “research patterns” on which to focus the attention to substantiate the project proposal (“Material and Immaterial Cultural Heritage”, “Natural Heritage”, “Agrifood Excellence”, “Tourism”, “Third Sector”, etc.). Only in this way is it possible to prefigure sustainable development scenarios respectful of the “spirit of the place” - in the meaning of “indelible” and “distinctive character” of Norberg-Schulz (Norberg-Schulz, 1980) - and of the values that express the relationship that, over the centuries, has linked local communities with the natural context in which they have lived. In particular, the World Heritage Committee, in the Vienna Memorandum of 2005, places the “spirit of the place” as a fundamental factor for improving the quality of life and increasing vitality and social cohesion, also with a view to increasing economic prosperity (World Heritage Committee, 2005, art.16). It considers the “emotional connection” which has regulated the relationship between man and the environment and which, especially in this area, has produced a perfect ecosystemic balance between human and natural components. This balance is based on a circular relationship thanks to which man has integrated himself into the environmental context respecting its rhythms and characteristics and from which he has received in exchange gifts from the earth and high quality of life.

For the Medways project in Cilento, the conservation of existing values and the production of “new” values passes through the rediscovery of the cultural resources of the Cilento territory, including natural capital and social capital, understood not only as a reconnaissance activity but as a process of recreation of material and immaterial values. Its aim is to identify the elements of permanence that substantiate the “intrinsic value” of the Cilento territory and that, therefore, represent the directions in which future development strategies should be oriented.

The project aims to trace both the intangible relationships, explicit or to be reconstruct, and the physical traces between the different “nodes”, which are also bearers of beauty and identity values. Just think of the network of secondary routes (some of them are already surveyed and marked), the ancient roads of medium age, pilgrimage routes, or even the roads of taste, the oil routes, etc. These routes not only represent a physical link but also have a value of testimony and education: along them runs an immense heritage of knowledge that must be experienced, protected and enhanced in its entirety (flora, fauna, agro-food resources, etc.). The knowledge of the most authentic value of the Cilento ecosystem, in any forms in which it is expressed, is an irreplaceable condition for any action aimed to increase the degree of socio-economic and cultural vitality of a territory and is a direction to follow for a proposal of protection and enhancement.

The above would not only allow the recovery and strengthening of a little-known heritage of knowledge but would also attract a portion of users interested in an “experiential tourism”, that enhances the local resources through a direct fruition.

This “culture of naturalness” in the time has made increasingly attractive the Cilento area and its lifestyle, because it promotes the rediscovery of slower rhythms, more attentive to nature and environment and inseparably linked to the exaltation of the cultural and food and wine traditions of the territory. This reality, today branded with the name of “Slow City”, represents the true essence of living in Cilento (although only three municipalities in Cilento are part of the network).

THE CIRCULAR ECONOMY MODEL FOR HUMAN-CENTERED AND SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT

The project is based on a particular perspective, based on the cultural heritage and cultural landscape as “great deposit of beauty” (Fusco Girard and Nocca, 2019), i.e. as an attractor from which to start again to recalibrate and promote a strategy of circular, human and sustainable development (Gravagnuolo et al., 2017). It has been recognized at European level as a fundamental economic resource in global competition, whose intrinsic value can be exploited through the adoption of new culture-based business and governance models (Presidenza Italiana del Consiglio dell’Unione Europea, 2014).

The approach of the historical urban landscape finds in the perspective of the circular economy a solution to “manage change”, with the aim of extending the useful life of resources as much as possible. The circular economy model in coherence with the HUL approach, and before that with the Burra Charter (ICOMOS 1979, 2013) encourages the creation of a “community of relationships”, which is a relevant element in determining the quality of life, but also for the generation of new economic value chains (Fusco Girard et al., 2017).

The intrinsic value, as an expression of a permanent and self-generating identity, is a cooperative, collaborative, solidarity-based value. Therefore, the circular economy, promoting efficiency and co-evolution together, is also the economy of the community and shows with clear empirical evidence that *«cooperation is economically, socially, ecologically convenient»* (Fusco Girard, 2014), because it manages to extend the time horizon of choices to the long term. In this sense, the circular economy is interpreted as an economy that safeguards the beauty, as a co-evolutionary economy, that promotes the cooperation, the solidarity, and the long-term actions (Fusco Girard and Nocca, 2019). The quality of the landscape, therefore its beauty, expressed by tangible and intangible elements, depends on the density of circular processes, that today is the ability to regenerate its “connective infrastructure” (Fusco Girard, 2018), to reconstruct the community relations through the renewal and updating of cultural memory.

Fig.5. and Fig.6.: The olives’s cultivation is one of the oldest in the Cilento and also one of the most famous thanks to the high-quality products derived from it. it reflects the “culture of naturalness” that characterizes the “Cilento model” and that respects the rhythms of nature (Photos by Olimpia Niglio and Osvaldo Marrocco).

This “culture of naturalness” has made the “Cilento model” unique and extraordinarily relevant to face the actual challenges caused by the ecological debt: in fact, it is perfectly in line with the principles of “circular economy”, which is the basis of the rural economy typical of Cilento. This economic model is inspired by the organizational cycles/processes of nature that, by reducing waste, avoids the accumulation of waste/waste and allows the system to support itself by continuously regenerating over time. The perspective of the circular economy represents a social regenerative process able to enhance the landscape and, at the same time, to generate economic prosperity.

The present project intends to propose some strategies for the regeneration of the city based on the model of the circular economy, which has characterized the millenary history of the Cilento villages.

The logic behind the circular economy model is implemented in urban regeneration processes through strategies and actions of adaptive reuse of abandoned, degraded or disused goods. This is the great challenge of regeneration processes in cities, which not only has an immaterial value but also a physical dimension. Today we are witnessing the presence of a large percentage of cultural heritage, especially ecclesiastical heritage, in a state of abandonment or underutilization, destined to remain in a situation of degradation due to lack of financial resources in the administrations to be allocated to the maintenance and recovery of these assets. They are “common goods”, as bearers of identity values, custodians of memory: their degradation corresponds to a progressive corrosion of the collective memory of the community that determines the loss of a part of its identity (Bosone, 2019).

Fig.7. (on the left): The watchtower of the “Mazza Elleni” (today property of Pietro Mazzarella) in San Mauro Cilento. Fig.8. (in the centre) and Fig.9 (on the right): In the “service room” there is a polychrome decorative band of the walls behind the ceiling and the Mazzarella coat of arms (Photos and description by Osvaldo Marrocco).

A reconnaissance of the cultural heritage of Cilento in a state of abandonment/degradation/underuse is therefore necessary, not only to understand its

consistency but also and above all to understand its role and importance within the project. This awareness could open new scenarios for the reuse of these assets, favoring the proposal to recover them through the establishment of functions that may be different from the original one but capable of respecting the “intrinsic value” of the buildings. This process involves the communities and all local stakeholders through “cultural meetings with the territory” (as defined in the project actions) not only for the identification of the assets with an identity value, but also to define a hierarchy of new preferable uses derived from their needs, respecting the “intrinsic value” of the asset (Fusco Girard and Gravagnuolo, 2018). The operational strategy of adaptive reuse of cultural heritage have to focus on the relationship between intrinsic value and use values. In this perspective, the evaluation activity plays a fundamental role in identifying the processes that succeed in “multidimensional productivity” (Gravagnuolo et al., 2017) of the different alternatives and their impacts, going beyond the perspective that reduces cultural heritage to mere archaeological or museum finds.

This process aims to transform cultural heritage and landscape into a resource, rather than a cost for the community.

The project, starting from already existing experiences (for example the european project Horizon2020 “Circular models Leveraging Investments in Cultural heritage adaptive reuse”²), aims to map and understand the trends already taking place at local level, identifying existing reuse projects and evaluating them on the basis of their respect for the “spirit of the places”. This mapping activity is useful to draw limits and potential of these practices, identifying which elements are replicable and transferable into the project proposal. In Cilento many historical buildings have changed their use (totally or partially) to host accommodation or cultural functions (e.g. the Castle of Capano Princes, in which are located the International Centre for the Mediterranean Diet “Angelo Vassallo” and the Regional Observatory for the Mediterranean Diet), reactivating the economy of many small villages, creating jobs opportunity above all for young people.

This type of action would enable the activation of territorial regeneration processes conducted by the communities themselves, strengthening those already existing, and promoting the full realization of the potential attractions not yet fully come to light. These actions configure a cultural project capable of regenerating trust between the individual and the community to which he belongs, between the institutions and between these and the people. Regenerating heritage in order to regenerate trust is the foundation of a collaborative and synergistic process to promote a good functioning of the institutions, a wise management of resources and also have positive effects for the market (creation of new activities and new jobs).

Finally, it would represent a concrete action to counter the phenomenon of depopulation of internal areas by re-establishing the link between community and heritage/cultural landscape. In this way it is possible to increase the communities’ awareness of the value of their heritage, nourishing in them the sense of “attachment to places” that stimulates them to implement actions of care and to become key players in the processes of recovery and enhancement.

² www.clicproject.eu

TOWARDS A DIGITAL-BASED CULTURAL VALORIZATION

Globalization, digitization and the progressive diffusion of new technologies are changing the way in which cultural heritage is produced, presented, made accessible and used, by new opportunities and new challenges for resource sharing. These changes are leading to an evolution of the economic, cultural and social value of heritage, requiring policies and governance solutions more innovative than so far adopted, for an economic “human” growth oriented to the welfare of citizens. In the current communication modes the digitization of culture is increasingly taking on the characteristics of a process of fruition as well as of knowledge and, if well conducted, can facilitate the involvement of wider segments of the community, also capturing the interest of young people. In this perspective, the involvement of schools assumes a fundamental role not only for their educational function but also for the possibility to activate further opportunities for experimentation by intercepting specific funding for school projects (PON, POR, Scuola Viva, etc.). This would guarantee moments of higher education, oriented to critical comparison and free exchange of ideas in a seminar and interdisciplinary context.

Starting from the awareness that knowledge is at the basis of conservation, valorization and development processes, a necessary step is precisely to produce critical knowledge, through the activities of the “MedWays Cilento Permanent Research Laboratory” and the “Permanent Laboratories on traditional and digital cultures”.

In the “digital culture” project, the activation of “Cultural Meetings”, which could become “Permanent Workshops on traditional and digital cultures”, plays a central role. They represent an opportunity (through interventions by experts, study seminars, refresher courses and thematic lessons) to unsaturated a dialogue between the extraordinary opportunities provided by the conscious use of the network and the history of the customs and traditions of the Cilento territory. The creation of a “virtual square”, a place of meeting and exchange, would favour the collection of information but also its implementation in a unique project that, on the one hand, recovers and enhances this capital of knowledge, and on the other, creates new forms of value and transmission of knowledge, in innovative ways and in step with the times. The involvement of generations of young people in the use of these methods, rather than “weakening” cultural content, will make it possible to revitalize and enrich it through new keys of interpretation, facilitating access and sharing and stimulating knowledge on the part of broader user groups.

In this sense, the involvement of young people is fundamental not only in the processes of recognition, knowledge and awareness of the value of their heritage but also as active players in the process of transfer and external dissemination.

Young people can thus assume the role of main promoters of the resources of their territory in the dual role of heirs of traditional knowledge but also as innovators of knowledge based on their digital knowledge.

“MEDWAYS CILENTO” PROJECT: THE OVERALL STRUCTURE

In addition to the general objectives outlined above, the project also focuses on specific objectives, organized in “Work Packages” and their respective “Tasks”. Some activities foreseen by the project can be activated immediately, for example the activation of a “MedWays Cilento Permanent Research Laboratory”, the establishment of a “Network of Municipalities of Ancient Cilento” and meetings with local stakeholders.

Other activities, on the other hand, have a medium-long term horizon and are expected to be carried out not only during the project but also afterwards, for example the Creation of a website and social profiles and the creation of a web platform, dedicated to Ancient Cilento.

It is expected that the project will last three years and that it, rather than representing a research that ends in itself, is instead an opportunity to set the right conditions so that the development processes activated are long-lasting and can be carried out by the network of actors established thanks to the project.

WP1 Mapping and valorization of the cultural memory of “Ancient Cilento”

This Work Package builds a common framework of knowledge based on a culture-based strategy for the promotion and enhancement of the heritage/cultural landscape of the “Ancient Cilento”. The aim is to increase the knowledge and awareness of the communities about the value of their cultural heritage, and to educate them on the conservation and enhancement of this heritage, to allow its transmission to future generations. The perspective is oriented to the elaboration of sustainable development scenarios focused on the “humanization” of cities and territories, and respectful of the intrinsic value of places.

The main objective of this Work Package is therefore to activate long-term synergies both among local stakeholders and between them and the research team in order to build a network of virtuous relationships capable of fostering a profitable cultural exchange in order to develop a feasible and shared short, medium and long term action plan.

This objective is achieved through the involvement of local stakeholders in the collection and organization of Cilento’s Material and Immaterial Cultural Heritage, in collaboration with the Superintendence ABAP of Salerno and Avellino and the National Institute for Intangible Heritage, and its communication, promotion and enhancement as an engine of economic and social development.

The systematization of data regarding the Cilento’s Material and Immaterial Cultural Heritage represents an important output of the project not only to organize the baggage of knowledge built up over time but also to make it more accessible and understandable.

The collection, analysis and classification of good practices in Cilento (pilot projects) inspired by the circular economy model is a fundamental step for the definition of implementation strategies consistent with this model.

Finally, this WP aims to activate a participatory planning process for the rediscovery and enhancement of the cultural heritage of ancient Cilento through a series of workshops with local stakeholders. The co-design aims to increase the awareness and the planning and entrepreneurial skills of both individuals and communities, bringing to full realization the local human capital.

Tasks:

T1.1 Activation of a “MedWays Cilento Permanent Research Laboratory” through coordination with universities, laboratories, and local, national and international research centres.

T1.2 Establishment of a “Network of Municipalities of Ancient Cilento” and design of an Action Plan for the network for the short, medium and long term.

T1.3 Systematization of knowledge: creation of a database based on the mapping of Cilento’s Material and Immaterial Cultural Heritage (pilot projects).

T1.4 Identification of good practices of reuse and valorization of the tangible and intangible cultural heritage of inland and rural areas (pilot projects) inspired by the circular economy model.

T1.5 Strategic participatory planning (workshops, laboratories, meetings with local stakeholders) for the rediscovery and enhancement of the cultural and natural heritage of ancient Cilento and for the identification of good practices in Cilento (pilot projects).

WP2 Continuous training for the promotion of the “Cilento model” and the enhancement of the territory and cultural heritage of Cilento

This WP aims to activate a continuous training process for the promotion of the “Cilento model” and the enhancement of the territory and cultural heritage of Cilento. This model is characterized by a culture of naturalness that places it perfectly in line with the principles of the “circular economy”, which are the basis of the rural economy typical of Cilento, inspired by the organizational cycles/processes of nature that, by reducing waste, avoids the accumulation of waste/waste and allows the system to support itself by continuously regenerating over time. The perspective of the circular economy is here proposed as a social regenerative process able to enhance the landscape and, at the same time, to generate economic prosperity.

Starting from the understanding and analysis of the virtuous life models of the past, the project aims at defining implementation strategies inspired by the circular economy model, which has always been the foundation of the “Cilento model” and which permeates the lifestyle of local communities. The teaching that comes from this model is an essential starting point to fight the culture of waste and to enhance the local material and immaterial cultural heritage, starting regenerative actions also for the hinterland areas that are not very developed.

Promote processes of digital-based cultural enhancement to promote knowledge and transmission of the cultural heritage of Cilento, especially through the involvement of schools to raise awareness among young people to love, respect and safeguard their cultural heritage, be protagonists of the social and cultural life of their territory, regain their roots and traditions, cultivating a sense of social and civil responsibility.

This objective will be achieved through the organization of training activities on the digitalization of cultural heritage and promotion of Cilento’s traditions and production activities related to the agri-food sector (Seminars, Summer Schools, Training Internships, Workshops, Lectio Magistralis, etc.). To this end, schools are expected to be involved in all project activities and agreements with universities or other training institutions to start internships or internships in the areas covered by the project activities.

Tasks:

T2.1 Understanding and analysis of the virtuous life models of the past inspired by the model of circular economy and intangible cultural heritage of Ancient Cilento through inspections, interviews with privileged interlocutors (testimonies of elderly people and residents, contact with associations of the territory also through web) and consultation of private (private collections) and public archives (libraries, municipal archives, Superintendence).

T2.2 Systematization and digitization of cultural heritage through the creation of a database.

T2.3 Promotion of Cilento’s traditions (poetry, music, dances, Mediterranean diet) through the organization of events and conferences, scientific production (articles), web communication,

projects with schools and involvement also of foreign academic institutions interested in starting a process of internationalization.

T2.4 Promotion of productive activities related to the agro-food sector (circular agriculture, fishing, typical local products) through the organization of events and conferences, scientific production (articles), web communication, projects with schools and involvement also of foreign academic institutions interested in starting a process of internationalization.

T2.5 Activation of agreements with universities or training institutions for internships or traineeships in the activities foreseen by the project.

T2.6 Involvement of Schools in project activities by intercepting specific funding for school projects (PON, POR, Scuola Viva, etc.).

WP3 Implementation of pilot projects with enterprises and startups

The objective of the WP is to test at least 5 pilot projects in the Ancient Cilento area for the rediscovery and enhancement of the local cultural heritage, through the involvement of local and international companies and startups for the creation of a virtuous network able to internationalize the “Cilento model” and to stimulate collaboration and co-design between different subjects.

Tasks:

T3.1 Call and selection of 5 pilot projects to develop and implement.

T3.2 Development of 5 prototypes of new products and services.

T3.3 Testing and validation with local companies and startups.

T3.4 Dissemination of results obtained.

WP4 Assessment and monitoring of impacts

The aim of this WP is the development of an evaluation framework based on criteria and indicators of impact of MedWays project and related actions and projects, shared by local stakeholders in order to test, implement, validate and share the innovative “circular” models developed by the project.

Tasks:

T4.1 Definition of a matrix of criteria and indicators to assess the multidimensional impacts of culture-based territorial regeneration processes starting from the analysis of the good practices analyzed.

T4.2 Collection and analysis of data for the *in itinere* evaluation of the impacts of the project based on the matrix of criteria and indicators previously defined.

WP5 Dissemination and communication of the contents and promotion of the project results

The general objective of this WP is to disseminate, communicate and promote the contents and results of the project at national and international level. The WP will be developed through the organization of communication and dissemination activities in different ways not only to promote the knowledge and transmission of the project, but also to facilitate interaction with other national

and international realities interested in the project, also in order to replicate the experience by adopting the models and approaches developed by the project.

Tasks:

T5.1 Creation of a website and social profiles for project promotion, dissemination and communication of project contents and activities.

T5.2 Professional and amateur digital productions (videos, short films, commercials) and scientific publications.

T5.3 Organization of events (temporary exhibitions, participation in festivals, etc.) to encourage the promotion and dissemination of the Cilento Cultural and Natural Heritage and to create opportunities for awareness and education, as well as national and international collaboration with other realities that could be a support for the project.

T5.4 Creation of a web platform, dedicated to Ancient Cilento, which has the dual role of both collating and systematizing all the cognitive heritage that will emerge during the project, promoting the knowledge and transmission of traditional knowledge, and acting as a “virtual square” to facilitate interaction between local productive realities. It is imagined that the platform can continue to be active even after the end of the project and that it can continue to be a tool at the service of the territory.

T5.5 Coordination with other local, national, and international initiatives.

WP6 Project Management

The aim of this WP is to ensure that the project achieves its objectives on time, on budget and with high quality results. The monitoring phase of the project is fundamental and will be structured according to interim and annual reports on the results obtained and expected.

Tasks:

T6.1 Project organization and planning (communication plan, risk plan, activity plan, etc.).

T6.2 Interim and annual reports on results achieved and expected.

CONCLUSION

The contribution of culture to the sustainable development deserves special attention and a qualitative leap in the perception of its social and economic impacts, especially today, a time in which economies, affected by the pandemic, are called not only to rebuild, but to reconvert «*along the lines of environmental neutrality, economic digitization, social inclusion*» (Fabrini, 2020).

Some experiences already done have demonstrated that the culture-led regeneration processes product also economic impacts, both in terms of the potential reduction of health costs for public spending for the well-being generated in the population involved, and in terms of the development of new services and professions.

The rediscovery of our cultural heritage and the recognition of its identity value, which makes it so indispensable for our memory, influences the relational aspects of our communities, the strengthening of resources (empowerment) and the capacity for learning, developing the “life skills” necessary for self-realization (World Health Organization, 1994). It enables the individual to

cope effectively with the demands and challenges of everyday life, increasing his adaptive capacity and improving his transversal personal skills, such as creative thinking, the ability to work in a team, stress management, conflict resolution.

For this reason, the project Medways Cilento is an open process that, guided by culture, promotes dialogue between different skills and social inclusion for the full development of human capital in the most marginal territories.

The circular economy model encourages the creation of a “community of relationships”, capable of ensuring development processes not only consistent with the past, with identity, with memory - therefore with the “intrinsic value” - but also generative of new values.

The circular economy approach, promoting efficiency and coevolution together, it represents the only strategy capable of expressing and enhancing value intrinsic to a settlement system, renewing its self-generative potential as a cooperative, cooperative, supportive value.

The circular economy can be defined as “community economy” that demonstrates how investing in a permanent identity based on cooperation can produce economic benefits (because it reduces the costs of production processes and allows a redistribution of wealth between all those involved), social (because it offers new job opportunities) and environmentally friendly (because it activates more sustainable processes for the environment and reduces negative impacts on it) (Fusco Girard, 2014), allowing the time horizon of choices to be extended to the long term.

The objective of the project is to take culture as a driver of change and development, an element capable of opening the horizons of intercultural dialogue while ensuring the protection and enhancement of local specificities.

In this perspective the research group will encourage new forms of cultural cooperation between research institutes, universities and exchanges of workers and experts from all over the world.

The project aims to meet the following needs of the various actors, prefiguring a hybrid model of information/decision capable of to strengthen the process of social empowerment and make it lasting through concrete actions in the territories. in this way the outlined methodological path can open the way to a process of enrichment and cultural integration, representing a virtuous model that can be replicated in other contexts.

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